

Rac-5h

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xl-3-99-rac-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	8	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 99 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	255.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 255.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/31/2022 9:50:13 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/1/2022 3:06:19 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	14.293	2766376	50.40	90523
2	16.156	2722433	49.60	75633

Asy-5h

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xl-3-99-asy-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	33	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 99 ASY
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	255.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 255.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/31/2022 10:15:34 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/1/2022 3:08:20 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	14.288	219435	4.01	7296
2	16.094	5258346	95.99	150478